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Use of Mobile Phones as an E-Learning tool in Teaching and Learning of English Language

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Abstract

Electronic learning (E-learning) is one of the modalities of modern pedagogy that makes use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) to help the learners in their knowledge construction process. Among ICT supporting e-learning appliances, mobile phones/smart phones are one of the fastest growing technological gadgets, popularly used as mobile learning (m-learning) devices. Many research scholars have found significant educational value of mobile phones in teaching and learning of English language in their studies. This article attempts at exploring the teachers' and students' perception towards mobile phones, their role in English language teaching and learning (ELTAL) and the factors influencing their integration in the Nepalese school education context. Based on the empirical study in five higher secondary schools, by collecting data through survey-based questionnaire from English language teachers and students as the participants, the study disclosed that mobile phones were relatively more familiar and highly accessible among participants than any other commonly used e-learning tools. Though Internet connectivity and pedagogical training were the most influencing factors in their ELTAL, most of the participant's perceived mobile phones as useful tools for improving English language skills, grammar, and vocabulary.

Keywords: *e-learning, m-learning, synchronous, language skills*

Introduction

The pedagogy used in the educational institutions in recent years has been tremendously modified due to the advancement in science and technology. The education innovators have created several kinds of learning applications by utilizing all sorts of new technological tools. The face-to-face mode of teaching and learning now has been old-fashioned, and the trends like distance learning, e-learning, blended learning, and mobile learning have been introduced as emerging learning environments (Moore, Dickson-Deane, & Gaylen, 2011). Many of the well-off educational institutions have integrated a learning management system (LMS) to create

a good e-learning environment. The use of new technological applications such as web 2.0 has been a preferred learning approach for receiving and processing information easily and quickly for the students of the digital native generation (Forment, Guerrero, & Poch, 2010). Several research studies have disclosed that the integration of the latest e-learning tools and technologies like mobile learning and mobile phones/Smartphone's in the educational activities has outstanding utilities in such modern pedagogical trends to ensure learning opportunities anytime, anywhere (Habbash, 2015).

More recently, the wireless, portable, and handheld technological tools have incrementally spread over educational practices across both developed and developing worlds (Traxler, 2007). The wireless mobile devices (WMDs) have attracted the users with their characteristic features like wireless connectivity and data gathering and processing abilities. Such technological devices have facilitated to mediate a wide range of learning activities and that they have expanded the classroom learning to 'real world learning' (Cochrane & Bateman, 2010). In the context of language teaching and learning, such technologies have generated several new possibilities and opportunities. According to Evans (2009, p. 28), "It would seem fairly uncontroversial to argue that language teaching and learning can benefit from the mediation of technology". More particularly, English language learners can be much benefitted with the use of such technologies because the Internet-assisted tools and technologies offer opportunities of a lot of exposure to the English language from where the learners can find sufficient comprehensible input (Chapelle, 2003). The learners can use different technological devices for several English language learning activities such as exploring and investigating, responding and integrating, reflecting and evaluating, composing and creating, presenting and performing, and communicating and collaborating (Pim, 2013). Mobile phones among such mobile technologies are more easily portable and ubiquitous which can be used for a broad range of educational and social communication activities (Nalliveetil & Alenazi, 2016). The integration of mobile phones in English language teaching and learning as an e-learning device has been an interesting field of study for many of the research scholars.

1. E-learning, m-learning, and mobile phones

The modalities of learning such as e-learning, distance learning, online learning, m-learning are sometimes confusing, but these have different distinct characteristics (Moore, Dickson-Deane, & Gaylen, 2011).

Distance learning is a broader term that includes e-learning as its subset; and m-learning is a subset of e-learning (Zouhair, Elhabib, & Abderrahim, 2016). The term 'e-learning' simply refers to learning with electronic media. E-learning differs from distance learning in that the former is specific to electronic media while the latter makes use of both electronic and print media. Online learning, on the other hand, is a newer improved version of distance learning in which learning is delivered using the Internet technology.

M-learning is a new modification of distance learning. Farley, Murphy, and Rees (2013) define m-learning as 'an e-learning activity that allows inclusion of mobile devices' (p. 287) According to Traxler (2007), "Mobile learning or mobile education is learning delivered or supported solely or mainly by handheld and mobile technologies such as personal digital assistants (PDAs), Smartphone's or wireless laptop personal computers (PCs)" (p. 4). It is the activity to obtain or provide educational content by means of wireless technological devices that have handheld mobility.

One of the most important characteristics of m-learning with mobile technology is that it helps to access knowledge and information 'anytime, anywhere' more conveniently. A fixed predetermined location and time are not required for m-learning, and it is often driven by curiosity and necessity (Traxler, 2010). M-learning is more flexible, a student-centered new learning strategy that makes learning informal, independent, and collaborative (Aamri & Suleiman, 2011). M-learning activity can be both synchronous and asynchronous and that it supports the delivery of ample multimedia content. Therefore, m-learning has been more popular nowadays, and many research studies have been conducted in order to investigate the ways of integrating mobile learning devices such as cellular Smartphone's, tablets, phablets, netbooks, notebooks, MP3 players, PDAs, and laptops in the teaching-learning activities (Wong, 2014).

The communication of messages through social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and sharing information using the tools like YouTube, Blog, and Skype have become a part of everyday life of the modern people. The e-learning device mobile phones can excessively be used for all these activities of communication. Mobile phones are found mostly owned and used by the people as they are relatively cheaper and that they provide lots of application tutors, and suitable learning platforms (El-Hussein & Cronje, 2010). They are popular because they are wireless, portable, and they possess the features such as ownership, individuality, and personalization (Traxler, 2010). Therefore, the number of mobile

phones has surpassed the number of computers and other electronic gadgets (Nalliveetil & Alenazi, 2016). In recent years, e-learning, mobile learning and mobile phones are spreading faster in the Nepalese societies and educational institutions too.

2. E-learning and English language teaching at secondary schools in Nepal

The English language is being taught and learnt as one of the core components of school education curriculum in Nepal (Curriculum Development Centre [CDC], 2007). Though being small (1,47,181 sq. km area) and landlocked, Nepal is a multi-cultural and multi-lingual country where 125 kinds of castes of people speak 123 varieties of mother languages; and English is one of them for a very small number of people (Central Bureau of Statistics [CBS], 2012). However, English has a different position among all these languages. It is because English is not just simply a means of communication as many other languages, it is used as lingua-franca internationally; it is the language of science and technology, and of many of the published books and websites (Harmer, 2007). The Ministry of Education (MOE) in Nepal has realized this fact, and considerable priority has given to English in the school curriculum. English is taught as one of the compulsory subjects from grade one up to Bachelor (diploma) level in community schools and colleges. It is also that, many students prefer studying English as an optional subject from grade one upwards. The institutional schools give much emphasis to English and many of them use it as the medium of instruction (Shrestha, 2008).

However, English language teaching and learning (ELTAL) in school education in the context of Nepal is a great challenge both socio-linguistically and methodologically (Shrestha, 2008). There are many problems related to infrastructural management, teachers, students, and teaching-learning environment. Still, many of the schools have not been able to upgrade themselves from using 'chalk and blackboard' to using 'marker and whiteboard' as the main teaching-learning instruments in the classroom. Only a few affluent schools in the urban area make use of the tools like laptop and multimedia projector. Mostly, the teachers are overworked; and that they lack appropriate instructional materials and refresher training. In most of the cases in the community schools, the students study English one period a day (45 minutes approximately), there is no such environment where they can get needed exposure to English. Students are limited to study the single textbook and are fully teacher depended for the information/resource materials. The access to information

or content is too narrow and there are often no interactive and collaborative exercises in teaching language skills. Teaching and learning English using the traditional methods such as grammar translation and structural drills has been the useless investment of time and effort (Shrestha, 2008). The fact is that such methods and techniques, and environment cannot help the learners to be a competent English language user (Bhattarai, 2006).

However, for some years now, consciousness has been aroused and it has been realized that it is necessary to bring a drastic change in the materials, methods, and the techniques that have been used in English language teaching (ELT). The MOE has considered e-learning technologies to play a significant role for the improvement of the access of information and for enhancement of collaborative learning; and for skills development of the learners (MOE, 2013). It is because the integration of e-learning tools or ICTs in ELTAL is supposed to be one of the effective strategies to bring a significant modification in the existing educational system from traditional 'teacher-centered' to more interactive 'student-centered' (Cooper & Zmud, 1990). Consequently, the Government of Nepal has increased the amount of the investment on ICT management. A master plan called 'Information and Communication Technology in Education Master Plan (ICTEMP)' has been made to provide access to the Internet and other e-learning resources to each of the community schools (MOE, 2013). A provision of financial subsidy has been made for the schools those run information technology (IT) courses. ICT has been made one of the professional core courses in the Bachelor of Education curriculum (Faculty of Education [FOE], 2015).

Among the e-learning technologies, m-learning is more appropriate in the developing countries (Traxler & Kukulska-Hulme, 2005) because mobile phones are relatively more ubiquitous, cheaper, and portable; and has multi-level functions among the m-learning devices. Therefore, the concerned people are needed to be aware and be updated so as to utilize such effective modern innovative technologies like m-learning and mobile phones in order to create more interactional and creative educational environment in Nepal.

3. Purpose of the study and research questions

E-learning is still in its crawling stage in Nepal, there has been just initial progress in e-learning and m-learning technologies. Many of the stakeholders are not aware of the utilities of technologies in education; they have doubts about using ICTs and e-learning as educational approaches; and they hesitate to make an investment in it. Though many of the research

studies have shown that e-learning and m-learning can play significant role in teaching and learning of English (Rank, Warren, & Millum, 2011), most of these studies are based on the context of developed countries and less attention has been paid to study concerning the contexts of developing or underdeveloped countries. Moreover, research studies about the use of mobile phones in ELTAL in Nepalese school education context are lagging behind. Many of the teachers and students in Nepal are unknown about integrating technologies in teaching and learning, and many of them lack technological and pedagogical knowledge for the productive use of the e-learning tools due to the lack of sufficient research study evidences. Therefore, research studies and investigation about the use of e-learning and m-learning are much valuable for fostering awareness among the stakeholders. This study is an attempt to add some more contributions in this research gap.

The study of the use of the mobile phones and their integration in ELTAL in context of Nepal is the main concern of this research study. This study aims at exploring the secondary level English language teachers' and students' perception towards mobile phones, and finding out the ways that the teachers and students use them in ELTAL. It also aims at finding out the causes that affect the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL. The following research questions had been used as the guide lines to achieve the objectives of the study:

- (i) What is the secondary level English language teachers' and students' perception towards mobile phones?
- (ii) In what ways are mobile phones used in English language teaching and learning?
- (iii) What are the basic factors that affect the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL?

Literature Review: E-learning and Mobile phones in ELT

E-learning covers the use of a range of electronic technologies and multimedia resources within learning processes. However, E-learning is sometimes taken synonymously with online learning. According to Epignosis (2014), "E-learning is a computer-based educational tool or system that enables you to learn anywhere and at any time" (P. 5). Similarly, Nichols (2003) views that e-learning technological tools should be either web-based, web-distributed, or web-capable. In the past, however, e-learning was considered to be a way of delivering learning using the blend of computer-based methods like CD-ROM (Epignosis, 2014). Moore, Dickson-Deane, and Gaylen, (2011) opine that e-learning takes place by

means of different tools such as audio-tapes, videos, slideshows, word documents, CD-ROMs; and computer-based training (CBT) and web-based training (WBT) related technologies with or without using the Internet.

Among the E-learning tools, the use of mobile learning is growing faster world-wide in recent years. However, according to Traxler and Kukulska-Hulme, (2005), mobile learning is more feasible and pedagogically appropriate in the developing countries than in developed countries. The existing situation of the physical infrastructures and the cultural environment indicate that 'the prescription of m-learning rather than other forms of e-learning is more cautious in the developing countries than in the developed worlds' (as cited in Traxler, 2010, p.6). It has been argued that the infrastructural causes such as Internet connectivity, landline telephony, power supply, and rarity of PCs; and the cultural causes such as the practices of the institutions, expectations, and standard of their staffs, students and their wider communities are responsible factors which suggest that mobile learning is appropriate in such contexts.

Many research studies have found that mobile phones are useful e-learning device (Pim, 2013). Nalliveetil and Alenazi (2016) studied the perception of EFL (English as a foreign language) teachers and students using a questionnaire and a self-report inventory at Aljouf University, Saudi-Arabia. The study found that a majority of the teachers and the students had positive attitudes towards mobile phone in ELTAL. The finding was that the impact of the mobile phone in the student life was more dominant than other electronic gadgets. The mobile phone was useful for enhancing communication skills and makes the students independent of the teachers. They helped the teachers and the students in the teaching-learning of vocabulary, spelling, and pronunciation. The study, however, disclosed a need for addressing the issues of variations in using mobile phone software programmes, and effective methodology. Similarly, Habbash (2015) studied Saudi-Arabian EFL teachers' attitude towards the mobile phone and found that majority of the teachers were in favor of using the mobile phone in the classroom. A few of them, however, opined that the use of mobile phone in the classroom was risky as some of the students tended to misuse it.

Wang and Smith (2013) studied the perception of the Japanese University students and found that the majority of them preferred using mobile phones rather than personal computers (PCs). Using questionnaire and interview as the research tools, the study disclosed that mobile phones could help for developing reading and grammar abilities of the English language learners. The data also revealed that mobile learning could be

enhanced by providing appropriate materials, teacher monitoring, students involvement, and linking mobile learning to the formal course. Similarly, Pimmer (2012) studied the usefulness of Facebook along with mobile phone in Nepalese public and private universities and found it as an appropriate educational tool that could be used in both formal and informal contexts. Mobile phones helped to learn English while waiting for lunch at restaurants, travelling in the bus, or even while listening to a lecture. It was found more intensively used for information and communication practices than laptops.

Likewise, Aamri and Suleiman (2011) investigated the perception and attitude towards mobile phone of the students of Sultan Qaboos University, Oman. The result showed that the mobile phones were boons blessed if only handled them wisely. The use of mobile phones in the classroom was still limited, and that the stakeholders needed to be clear that mobile phones were more saint than sinner. In their study Yu, Lin, Huang, and Hsieh (2013) evaluated the use of mobile phone in ELT in Taiwan; and disclosed that the device was useful for improving listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills and mobile learning was more effective than traditional methods.

This review of related literature has provided an insight that mobile phones are easily portable, and relatively more affordable m-learning devices. They can function as mini-computer and can be used both synchronously and asynchronously for various activities of ELTAL. Internet connectivity and pedagogical training are the fundamental requirements useful for the productive use of mobile phones.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework guiding this study is the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) model proposed by Mishra and Koehler (2006). TPCK is a teacher knowledge framework for technology integration introduced to address the perennial issue of what teachers need to know to teach effectively with ICTs. This model emphasizes the intersection between the development of knowledge (K) of the subject matter/content (C), with the knowledge of technology (T), and knowledge of pedagogy (P). The framework based on the constructivists' learning approach, stresses a good combination of appropriately selected technology with the experience of content matter and pedagogical approaches from the part of the teacher for successive learning to take place. The teacher's instruction can guide and direct the student' use of the

technological tools such as mobile learning devices and the mobile phones for improving their language skills.

Data and Methods

This study made use of both quantitative and qualitative information to make the research more comprehensive. For the collection of data, five higher secondary schools from Dhankuta district, Nepal, were chosen purposefully as the field of study (see Appendix II). The schools were chosen in order to capture the coverage of the geographical location of the higher secondary schools in the district. As the participants, two of the English language teachers were selected by means of purposive sampling from each school (N=10), who were requested to share their experiences of using mobile phones in ELT; and ten students studying English from grade XI from each school (N=50) were selected using random sampling methods. In this way, including the teachers and students, altogether 60 participants took part in this study.

As the research tool, a survey-based questionnaire with a set of 10 questions was prepared (see Appendix I). Much care was taken while constructing the questionnaire to ensure that the required information could be gained with information and responses given by the participants. The questionnaire consisted of two five-point Likert scale questions, three open-ended questions, and other five closed-ended questions so as to achieve the goals set in the objectives and the research questions of the study. The results of the data of the closed-ended questions were shown in charts and tables; and were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as average and percentage. Similarly, the responses to the open-ended questions were studied in depth several times, they were segmented and coded under specific themes, and conclusions were drawn by means of qualitative content analysis methods.

Results and Discussion

The results of the data and information collected have been shown in the table and graph; and have been analyzed, interpreted, and discussed based on the findings. The explanation and interpretation of the results have been presented in the following sub-headings in the succeeding paragraphs.

1. Perception of mobile phones

The results of the data analysis reveal that all the teachers, and 96% of the students possessed mobile phones and used it in their everyday life (see Fig 1). It is one of the most commonly used e-learning tools by both

the students and the teachers in their day to day activities. Another most common mobile device was the laptop which was used by 80% of the teachers and 30% of the students. Similarly, 30% of the teachers and 16% of the students used the tablet. The results in Figure 2 show that 60% of the teachers and 52% of the students used mobile phones one to two hours a day. Likewise, it was used up to one hour a day by 40% of the teachers and 36% of the students.

Figure 1: Most commonly used m-learning devices

The findings in Fig 1 and Fig 2 indicate that mobile phones were quite familiar to the teachers and the students. Most of them used them every day and the majority of them used them for more than one hour in a day. It reveals that the participants found useful materials/contents in their mobile phones for their day to day life. Mobile phones were primarily used for finding the news and information, for communication, and for entertainment. It was found that four percent of the students from rural area schools did not use mobile phones. One of the possible causes of it could be the poor economic status of their family.

Figure 2: Average hours spent a day on mobile phones

The findings indicate that mobile phones were used for several purposes such as making calls, sending SMS, downloading resources, recording the events, studying online or offline materials, and for social networking (see Table 1). All the participants who possessed mobile phones used them 'always' for making calls and for sending SMS. The social networking site Facebook was 'always' used by 20% of the teachers and 76% of the students. It was used 'usually' by 60% of the teachers and 12% of the students. Next site YouTube was always used by 76% of the students while 70% of the teachers used it 'usually'.

In response to the open-ended question 'Which of the m-learning devices do you prefer and why?', most of the participants preferred using mobile phones. Some of the most remarkable responses were:

"It has been a part of my life using mobile phones from early morning to going to bed. They are portable; I can use them for multiple purposes, though not so cheaper",

"It is wireless, it helps in many of the activities in my life like making calls and knowing the time. I use it for listening to news and songs, watching videos, reading newspapers and social networking"

The results in Table 1 and the participants' opinions of the open-ended questions revealed that both the teachers and the students had positive attitudes towards mobile phones, and they perceived them as useful and necessary devices in their life. It was found that mobile phones were relatively more popular among the students than among the teachers for the activities like watching YouTube videos and using Facebook. For those activities, many of the teachers could have used another device 'laptop' which was not easily available for many of the students. It could be interpreted that the 'resources and appropriation theory' (van Dijk, 2005) could have been applied in the context of the diffusion of technology.

Table 1: Most common activities and frequency of using mobile phones

Use of mobile phone	Activities	Always		Usually		Often		Sometimes		Never	
		T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%
General Purpose use	Making calls	100	96						4		
	Sending SMS	100	96						4		
	Recording							30	10	70	90
	Taking photo		64	80	32	20					4
	Playing games				68		16	70	12	30	4
	Listening to music				36	80	36	10	24	10	4
	Chatting				40		34	40	22	60	4
	Studying			70	44			28	30	24	4
	Offline materials										
Internet service use	Downloading/ Web-browsing					20	42	30	24	50	34

					40	20	60	42		38
	Using online dictionary				20	4	10	4		4
	YouTube	76	70	12	20	10	50	34	10	52
	Sending e-mail		20	4	20				100	100
	Video conference						10		90	100
	Working on LMS									4
Social Networking	Facebook	20	76	60	12	20	4	4	24	80
	Skype							20	28	60
	Twitter							40	28	80
	Imo							20	32	30
	Viber					20		20	24	60
	Blog									24
										72
										72
										68
										76

T= Teacher, S= student

2. Use of mobile phones in ELTAL

It was found that mobile phones were exploited in varieties of ways in teaching and learning of English. The results show that all the teachers' and 96% of the students used mobile phones for ELTAL purposes to some limit. Another device, laptops were used by the 60% of the teachers and 22% of the students. It was clear that the extent of the use of mobile phones for ELTAL was relatively much higher in comparison to other m-learning devices (see Fig 3).

Figure 3: Use of m-learning devices for ELTAL

The findings indicate that mobile phones had been used for teaching and learning of various aspects of the English language though its use was not so highly frequent. The teachers and the students used them most often for reading the resources/information and finding the word meaning. It was found that 70% of the teachers and 52% of the students 'usually' used mobile phones for the purpose of reading resources and information (see Table 2). For finding word meaning, 10% of the teachers 'always' used mobile phones, and 40% of them used it 'usually'. The results show that

44% of the students 'usually' used mobile phones for finding the word meaning. Similarly, 40% of the teachers used it for teaching listening and speaking skills 'usually', while 60% and 40% of them 'often' used them for accessing learning resources and learning grammar respectively. Likewise, 48% of the students 'often' used mobile phones for accessing resources/information and listening; while 36% and 34% of them 'often' used it for speaking and grammar related activities respectively.

The results in Figure 4 show the participants' use of the medium of language while using mobile phones. It indicated that a considerable number of the participants used English as the medium of language for learning resources and other information on their mobile phones. Altogether 50% of the teachers and 40% of the students used the English language for this purpose. It indicates that mobile phones had contributed to some extent for increasing the amount of exposure to English.

Table 2: Use of mobile phones for ELTAL

Language Area	Activities	Always		Usually		Often		Sometimes		Never	
		T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%	T%	S%
Vocabulary	Finding meaning	10		40	44	30	32	20	20		4
	pronunciation					60	34	40	42		24
	Learning spelling							60	36	40	64
Language Skills	Learning listening			40	28	50	48	10	16		8
	Learning speaking			40	24	50	36	10	16		24
	Learning reading			70	52	20	32	10	12		4
	Learning writing							20	10	80	90
Translation Grammar	Translating							30	10	70	90
	Practising grammar					40	34	60	46		16
Accessing Resources	Accessing learning resources					60	48	30	44	10	8

T= Teacher, S= student

With these findings shown in the Table and the Figures, it can be interpreted that the mobile phones were quite useful for the teachers and the students in their activities of English language skills learning. More particularly, the participants in the study reported that they found mobile phones useful for improving mostly reading, listening, vocabulary and grammar skills. However, the use of mobile phones for those activities was not so persistent. Some of the main causes of this were the unavailability of the Internet, and lack of their technological pedagogical skills. There was the problem of Internet access; and they needed to use their mobile data package which was not easily affordable. They could have used offline learning resources like offline dictionary, grammar or other downloaded

learning resources even with the limited Internet access, but just less than half of the students (44%) 'usually' did this (see Table 1). This lack of the effective integration of mobile phones in ELTAL might have been appeared due to inadequate technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) of the teachers and the students. The teacher's TPCK is a very crucial factor for the adoption and diffusion of the technologies (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

Figure 4: Mostly used the medium of language on mobile phones

However, by means of various online/offline software programmes, language games and quizzes, translation software, listening and reading materials; mobile phones provided learners with some amount of exposure to English, and they helped to develop the skills of an autonomous learner. It was also that mobile phones were found more popular in social networking like Facebook and Viber which helped them for improving communication skills.

3. Integration of Mobile Phones in ELTAL

The findings show that mobile phones were the most ubiquitous e-learning device among the teachers and students. However, the results reveal that the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL had not been 'usual'. There were different factors behind this. Fig 5 makes clear that the most common factors that affected the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL were related to infrastructural management, pedagogical skills and training, curriculum and textbook, and the availability of learning applications.

In the study, all the participants opined that problem with Internet connectivity was one of the main responsible factors that hindered using mobile phones for teaching and learning of English (see Fig 5). Another most important cause was the pedagogical skills and training related problem for using mobile phones in ELTAL Altogether 80 % of the

teachers, and 74 % of the students responded that they lacked pedagogical knowledge so as to utilize mobile phones for learning English. In the same way, 60 % of the teachers and 68 % of the students had their opinion that the curriculum and the textbook were not mobile phone user-friendly; while 40% of the teachers and 42% of the students expressed that the problem was the attitude towards mobile phones. Likewise, 30 % of the teachers and 42 % of the students opined that they did not find English learning resources that were course specific sufficiently enough to be used on their mobile phones.

Figure 5: Factors affecting the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL

Some of the remarkable excerpts from the participants' responses to the open-ended question related to the possible ways of effective integration of mobile phones in ELTAL are:

"I think the infrastructures like Internet connectivity and availability of English learning resources are the challenging factors affecting the integration of mobile phones in ELTAL. These should be made strong to improve the productive use of such devices."

"In my opinion, the teachers need some pedagogical training related to the strategies for the productive integration of mobile phones in ELTAL."

"As mobile phones are mostly available, the curriculum and textbook activities need to encourage the learners using these tools."

The findings of the data analysis and the participants' experiences in response to the open-ended questions make it clear that poor infrastructure management was the main problem for the effective integration of the technologies of e-learning and m-learning in the teaching and learning process. It had caused the problems of the digital divide like inequality in

the distribution of the resources and in the skills of using such resources and tools. Another equally important factor affecting the integration of e-learning was the technological pedagogical knowledge of the teachers and the students. Many of the teachers had not got any training about the pedagogical use of ICTs for teaching and learning of English. Likewise, mobile phone user-friendly curriculum/textbooks and learning applications; and ICT awareness of the stakeholders also were some of the responsible factors. Effective integration of the e-learning technologies required taking these problems into consideration.

Conclusion

Mobile phones are one of the most ubiquitous m-learning devices growing fast in the recent years in Nepal. Mobile phones are becoming more popular because of their features that they are wireless, portable, relatively cheaper, and they can have multi-level functions. They can fulfill some of the demands of the 'anytime anywhere' learning of the digital age in the Nepalese contexts. Most of the Nepalese teachers and students use them mostly for social communication purposes, and a considerable number use them in teaching and learning of English mainly for practicing vocabulary, grammar, and language skills; and accessing information or resources. Mobile phones have provided at least some amount of exposure to English, and they have helped to improve learner autonomy.

However, like several developing countries, the educational infrastructures for creating ICT-based teaching and learning environment have not been well managed in Nepal. There are several factors affecting the integration of mobile phones in the teaching and learning of English in the schools. Digital divide is one of the greatest problems that having possessed the devices, many of the teachers and the students know just a little about their productive utilization. Development of e-learning infrastructures and pedagogical training to the teachers and students are highly required for their effective integration in ELTAL activities.

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